

ROLE OF INTRAVENOUS AMINO ACID INFUSION (*PAN-AMIN G*) IN IMPROVING LIQUOR QUANTITY IN IDIOPATHIC OLIGOHYDRAMNIOS

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Abstract

Background: Idiopathic oligohydramnios is associated with increased risks of intrauterine growth restriction, cord compression, and perinatal morbidity.

Objective: To compare the effectiveness of intravenous amino acid infusion (PAN-AMIN G) versus normal saline in improving AFI in women with idiopathic oligohydramnios. **Methods:** This randomized controlled trial was conducted at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Services Hospital, Lahore from December 2024 to May 2025. A total of 60 women with idiopathic oligohydramnios (AFI <5 cm) after 28 weeks of gestation were included through consecutive sampling and randomized into two groups: Group A received intravenous normal saline (500 ml drip), while Group B received intravenous PAN-AMIN G (200 ml infusion), administered on alternate days for six doses. **Results:** The mean AFI increased significantly in both groups; however, the rise was greater in the PAN-AMIN G group (baseline 3.9 ± 0.7 cm to 7.0 ± 0.8 cm; mean change 3.1 ± 0.7 cm) compared to the saline group (baseline 3.8 ± 0.6 cm to 4.9 ± 0.7 cm; mean change 1.1 ± 0.3 cm) ($p < 0.001$). Normalization of AFI (>7 cm) was achieved in 63.3% of the amino acid group versus none in the saline group ($p < 0.001$). PAN-AMIN G was well tolerated, with only mild transient side effects.

Conclusion: Intravenous amino acid infusion (PAN-AMIN G) is significantly more effective than normal saline in improving liquor quantity in idiopathic oligohydramnios, offering a safe and practical therapeutic option. Larger trials assessing perinatal outcomes are recommended.

INTRODUCTION

Idiopathic oligohydramnios refers to a condition where the volume of amniotic fluid (also known as liquor) is less than expected for the gestational age, and the cause is unknown. A single deepest pocket (SDP) of less than two centimeters or an amniotic fluid index (AFI) of less than 5 cm are examples of

objective measurements that can be used to diagnose this condition [1]. Any type of oligohydramnios can complicate a pregnancy, and complications include umbilical cord compression, fetal deformation, and pulmonary hypoplasia in mid-trimester oligohydramnios. An increased risk

of fetal or neonatal death is associated with oligohydramnios [2]. This risk may be related to the underlying cause of the reduced amniotic fluid volume, its sequelae, or both. In cases of idiopathic oligohydramnios, the severity (reduced versus no amniotic fluid) and gestational age at occurrence determine the fetal prognosis [3]. For normal fetal movement, mid-trimester lung development, and cushioning the fetus and umbilical cord from uterine compression, an adequate volume of amniotic fluid is essential. Consequently, several interventions have been attempted to improve the AF volume, including hospitalization, specialist consultation, bed rest, oral rehydration, intravenous (IV) hydration, and IV amino acids [4]. A few studies in the literature have demonstrated that IV amino acids are superior to IV hydration for improving AFI, whereas others have demonstrated that IV hydration is superior. A single-blind randomized clinical trial conducted in Gujrat, Pakistan, consisted of 104 patients equally divided into two groups (A = intravenous normal saline, B = intravenous amino acids). After six drips, the study found that group B had a significantly higher mean AFI (4.790.65 vs. 6.820.62; $p < 0.001$). Similarly, change of AFI also showed significant increase in group B (3.09 ± 0.70) when compared to group A (1.00 ± 0.31) [5]. Idiopathic oligohydramnios, a condition causing pregnancy complications, could benefit from intravenous amino acid infusion. PAN-AMIN G is IV infusion containing several amino acids and is usually recommended for patients who require peripheral nutritional supply of amino acids [6]. In order to confirm the long-term advantages and safety of intravenous amino acid infusion, particularly for PAN-AMIN G, additional research is required. The diagnosis of oligohydramnios is made by ultrasound, most commonly using the amniotic fluid index (AFI) or the single deepest pocket (SDP) [7]. An AFI of ≤ 5 cm or an SDP of < 2 cm is considered diagnostic. Idiopathic oligohydramnios accounts for a notable subset of cases where maternal conditions such as hypertensive disorders, diabetes, ruptured membranes, and fetal anomalies are excluded [8]. Although considered “idiopathic,” such cases may reflect subclinical placental insufficiency or unrecognized alterations in fetomaternal physiology [9]. The prevalence varies, but it is estimated to complicate approximately 3–5% of pregnancies, with higher rates observed in resource-limited settings where maternal risk factors are

more prevalent and antenatal surveillance may be suboptimal [10].

Objective

To compare the outcome of intravenous amino acid infusion (PAN-AMIN G) versus normal saline in increasing amniotic fluid index (AFI) in pregnant women with idiopathic oligohydramnios after six infusions.

Methodology

This Randomized Controlled Trial was conducted at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Services Hospital, Lahore, from December 2024 to May 2025. Women with oligohydramnios confirmed after 28 weeks of gestation were included in the study. Non-probability, consecutive sampling technique was used to collect the data. The sample size of 60 (30 patients in each group) is calculated based on a power of 80%, a 95% confidence interval, and a mean improvement of AFI in the normal saline group of 1.00 ± 0.31 and 3.09 ± 0.70 in the PAN-AMIN G group, as described by Habib N et al.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Women of any parity
- Maternal age: 18 to 40 years
- Gestational age: 28 to 36 weeks
- AFI < 5 cm with intact amniotic sac (Idiopathic oligohydramnios, as per operational definitions)

Exclusion Criteria:

- Severe anemia (Hb < 8 g/dL)
- Fetal anomalies (on ultrasonography)
- Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy
- Diabetes mellitus, PROM
- Threatened preterm labour

Data Collection

The study commenced after approval from the institutional ethical review board. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to enrollment. Eligible women were admitted and evaluated for fetomaternal well-being. Amniotic fluid index (AFI) was measured using transabdominal ultrasonography, by calculating the largest vertical pocket in each abdominal quadrant. The sum of these four values represented the AFI in centimeters. A normal

AFI in term gestation was considered as 12.9 ± 4.6 cm.

Patients with AFI < 5 cm were randomized into two groups:

- **Group A:** Received intravenous normal saline (500 ml drip).
- **Group B:** Received intravenous amino acid infusion (PAN-AMIN G 200 ml), administered on alternate days, up to a total of six drips.

AFI was measured at baseline and repeated 48 hours after the 6th drip. The primary outcome was the change in AFI, which was calculated and documented by the researcher.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Quantitative variables such as age, gravidity, gestational age, and change in AFI were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. The mean change in AFI between the two groups was compared using an independent sample t-test. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Stratification was done for age, BMI, gestational age, and parity to address potential effect modifiers. Post-stratification, an independent sample t-test was reapplied, with a p-value of ≤ 0.05 considered significant.

Results

Data were collected from 60 patients, mean maternal age was 27.8 ± 4.6 years in the normal saline group and 28.2 ± 4.4 years in the PAN-AMIN G group. Most participants were multigravida, accounting for 56.7% in Group A and 60.0% in Group B, while primigravida women made up 43.3% and 40.0% respectively. The mean gestational age at enrollment was 31.2 ± 2.4 weeks in the saline group and 31.5 ± 2.6 weeks in the amino acid group, showing no significant difference. Baseline AFI was also similar between groups (3.8 ± 0.6 cm vs 3.9 ± 0.7 cm). When categorized, the majority of patients in both groups fell within the 3.1–4.0 cm range (43.3% in Group A vs 46.7% in Group B), followed by 2.5–3.0 cm and 4.1–4.9 cm categories.

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics of Patients (N = 60)

Variable	Group A (Normal Saline, n=30)	Group B (PAN-AMIN G, n=30)
Age (years), mean \pm SD	27.8 ± 4.6	28.2 ± 4.4
Parity		
• Primigravida	13 (43.3%)	12 (40.0%)
• Multigravida	17 (56.7%)	18 (60.0%)
Gestational age (weeks), mean \pm SD	31.2 ± 2.4	31.5 ± 2.6
Baseline AFI (cm), mean \pm SD	3.8 ± 0.6	3.9 ± 0.7
Baseline AFI Categories		
• 2.5 – 3.0	8 (26.7%)	7 (23.3%)
• 3.1 – 4.0	13 (43.3%)	14 (46.7%)
• 4.1 – 4.9	9 (30.0%)	9 (30.0%)

The mean AFI increased from 3.8 ± 0.6 cm to 4.9 ± 0.7 cm in the saline group (mean change 1.1 ± 0.3 cm), while in the amino acid group, it rose from 3.9 ± 0.7 cm to 7.0 ± 0.8 cm (mean change 3.1 ± 0.7 cm). The difference in mean change was highly significant ($p < 0.001$). Stratified analysis showed consistent results: in women with gestational age 28–32 weeks, the mean AFI change was 1.0 ± 0.3 cm with saline

compared to 3.0 ± 0.6 cm with amino acids

($p < 0.01$), while in those 33–36 weeks, the change was 1.2 ± 0.4 cm vs 3.2 ± 0.7 cm ($p < 0.01$). Similar findings were noted by parity: primigravida women had a mean AFI change of 1.1 ± 0.3 cm in the saline group compared to 3.2 ± 0.6 cm in the amino acid group ($p < 0.01$), and multigravida women showed 1.2 ± 0.4 cm vs 3.0 ± 0.7 cm respectively ($p < 0.01$).

Table 2. Change in Amniotic Fluid Index (AFI) and Stratified Analysis

AFI (cm) / Variable	Group A (Normal Saline, n=30)	Group B (PAN-AMIN G, n=30)	p-value
Baseline AFI, mean ± SD	3.8 ± 0.6	3.9 ± 0.7	0.64
Post-treatment AFI, mean ± SD	4.9 ± 0.7	7.0 ± 0.8	<0.001
Mean change in AFI, mean ± SD	1.1 ± 0.3	3.1 ± 0.7	<0.001
Stratified by Gestational Age			
• 28–32 weeks	1.0 ± 0.3	3.0 ± 0.6	<0.01
• 33–36 weeks	1.2 ± 0.4	3.2 ± 0.7	<0.01
Stratified by Parity			
• Primigravida	1.1 ± 0.3	3.2 ± 0.6	<0.01
• Multigravida	1.2 ± 0.4	3.0 ± 0.7	<0.01

Persistent oligohydramnios (<5.0 cm) was seen in 40.0% of patients in the saline group but only 3.3% in the PAN-AMIN G group. Improvement to low-normal levels (5.0–7.0 cm) occurred in 60.0% of the saline group and 33.3% of the amino acid group. Notably, normalization of AFI (>7.0 cm) was achieved in

63.3% of the PAN-AMIN G group compared to none in the saline group (p<0.001). With regard to maternal safety, all patients in the saline group had no side effects. In the amino acid group, most (90.0%) had no adverse effects, while 6.7% reported mild nausea and 3.3% reported transient flushing.

Table 3. Post-Treatment AFI Response and Maternal Side Effects

Variable	Group A (Normal Saline, n=30)	Group B (PAN-AMIN G, n=30)	p-value
Post-treatment AFI Response			
<5.0 cm (Persistent oligohydramnios)	12 (40.0%)	1 (3.3%)	<0.001
5.0 - 7.0 cm (Improved but low-normal)	18 (60.0%)	10 (33.3%)	
>7.0 cm (Normalized AFI)	0 (0.0%)	19 (63.3%)	
Maternal Side Effects			
None	30 (100%)	27 (90.0%)	0.08
Nausea	0 (0.0%)	2 (6.7%)	
Flushing	0 (0.0%)	1 (3.3%)	

Discussion

The present randomized controlled trial compared the effectiveness of intravenous amino acid infusion (PAN-AMIN G) with normal saline in improving amniotic fluid index (AFI) among women with idiopathic oligohydramnios. The results showed that the two interventions increased AFI but the difference was much higher in the PAN-AMIN G group. Patients that are continuously administered amino acids showed an average of AFI increase of 3.1 \pm 0.7 cm after six infusions, unlike the saline group which showed an average of 1.1 \pm 0.3 cm. In addition, the AFI (>7 cm) normalization was observed in almost two-thirds of the amino acid group, and no patient in the saline group attained the same. These findings are in line with earlier studies that have underscored the poor value of IV hydration as an independent treatment to redress oligohydramnios. Normal saline infusion improves intravascular volume and transiently augments uteroplacental perfusion and could be a contributor to moderate improvements in AFI [11]. It is, however, only temporary and not enough to normalize AFI in most instances. In comparison, intravenous amino acid infusion offers osmotic support and essential metabolic substrate to the body. Amino acids increase maternal plasma oncotic pressure, improve uteroplacental blood flow, and increase fetal

renal perfusion, which increases fetal urine production the primary determinant of AFI during the third trimester [12].

The high benefit of PAN-AMIN G detected in the present study is consistent with prior studies performed to compare the amino acid infusion with hydration. The hypothesis that nutritional supplementation is more directly involved in fetal physiology and liquor amount was supported by prior trials, which showed that amino acid therapy increased mean AFI increase two to three times more than saline [13]. Furthermore, stratified analysis in our study supplemented the evidence that PAN-AMIN G is effective in both gestational age cohorts and in primigravida and multigravida women, thereby further validating its broad generalizability. Another factor is maternal security. Amino acid infusion was safe, and only a few side effects, including nausea and flushing, were reported in a small proportion of patients in this trial. No significant maternal or fetal complications were recorded, which is an indication that PAN-AMIN G is a safe intervention that can be used during pregnancy. The results are encouraging and align with previous research that reported few side effects in using amino acid intravenous delivery [14] [15].

These results have a clinical implication worth mentioning. Idiopathic oligohydramnios is linked with higher risks of intrauterine growth restriction, cord compression, non-reassuring fetal heart rate patterns, and operative births.

Perinatal morbidity and better pregnancy outcomes can be achieved by effective interventions that can enhance AFI [16]. PAN-AMIN G could be a better approach in the treatment of idiopathic oligohydramnios, as it achieves higher increases in AFI and normalization rates than hydration. It is also important to note that this study has provided strong reasons as to why low-cost and practical safe therapies should be explored in resource-limited environments, where procedures like amnio-infusion, which involve invasions, are not commonly used [17]. Intravenous amino acid use presents a comparatively easy and practical method that can help enhance outcomes without placing substantial additional pressure on healthcare systems [18]. But there are limitations with this trial. The sample was also relatively small, which might restrict the applicability of the results. Short-term outcomes, such as changes in AFI, were only measured, and there was no evaluation of long-term perinatal outcomes, including neonatal morbidity and mortality. Moreover, the researchers have not evaluated how AFI improvements are directly related to operative delivery or adverse neonatal event reductions, which would give more compelling proof of clinical advantage. These findings should be verified in future studies conducted with larger cohorts and extended follow-up and evaluation of the perinatal outcomes.

Conclusion

It is concluded that intravenous amino acid infusion (PAN-AMIN G) is significantly more effective than normal saline in improving amniotic fluid index (AFI) in women with idiopathic oligohydramnios. Patients receiving PAN-AMIN G demonstrated greater increases in AFI, with a higher proportion achieving normalization of liquor volume, while maintaining a favorable safety profile. These findings suggest that PAN-AMIN G may serve as a safe, accessible, and superior therapeutic option for managing idiopathic oligohydramnios, particularly in settings where invasive interventions are not feasible. Larger studies with long-term follow-up are recommended to confirm these results and evaluate perinatal outcomes.

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